

An efficient numerical Model for Evaluation of the Whipping Influence on Fatigue Life of Structural Details of Floating Structures

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Abstract. Whipping refers to transient hull vibrations induced by impulsive wave loading, typically caused by slamming or wave slap. Accurate evaluation of slamming loads is critical in whipping analysis, yet the hydrodynamic modeling of slamming remains highly complex, particularly for 3D cases. Consequently, 2D slamming models, such as the Generalized Wagner model combined with the strip approach, are often employed despite their limitations, including unclear validity and high computational demands. This work introduces a simplified slamming model inspired by Korobkin's approach available in the literature. The slamming force is decomposed into three components dependent on impact speed, acceleration, and gravity, which are functions of the penetration depth for a given body shape. The force coefficients are precalculated using CFD simulations. This model is integrated with a classical diffraction-radiation model for seakeeping simulations, enabling the calculation of impact conditions in real-time. The methodology combines linear quasi-static and nonlinear dynamic whipping structural responses, allowing time-domain simulations of hull vibrations under specified operating conditions. Fatigue damage is evaluated for both quasi-static and combined responses using the rainflow counting method, and a fatigue reduction factor quantifies whipping effect. The method, implemented in an in-house tool SLAMA by integrating Bureau Veritas' HOMER tool and OpenFoam, is demonstrated on an FPSO, offering fast simulations to evaluate fatigue life across various operating conditions.

Keywords: *whipping, time domain simulations, linear spectral fatigue, nonlinear whipping response, FPSO.*

1 Introduction

Whipping is usually defined as the transient body vibrations induced by the impulsive wave loading. Most often the fatigue due to wave induced impulsive loading is of concern only and that is the case here too. The most critical point in the whipping analysis is the evaluation of the whipping inducing loads. The hydrodynamic modeling of whipping inducing loads is extremely complex and still no fully satisfactory numerical slamming model exists for the general 3D case. That is why the 2D slamming models (usually Generalized Wagner model), combined with the strip approach, are usually employed to evaluate wave induced vibrations. However, these simplified 2D models have several limitations and their domain of validity is still not fully clear and in addition the associated CPU time is still very high. In the present work we propose a simpler slamming model inspired by the work of Korobkin (more details in [1]) to estimate wave impulsive loading. In this model the wave induced force is assumed to be composed of three components which depend on the impact speed, acceleration and gravity respectively. For a given shape of the body, these components are functions of the penetration depth only. The associated force coefficients, for each part, are precalculated using the CFD simulations. This simple model is combined with the classical diffraction-radiation model for seakeeping simulations, which allows for the evaluation of the impact conditions in terms of the local penetration depth and the associated velocity and acceleration at each time instant. During the time domain simulations, the linear quasi static and nonlinear dynamic

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whipping structural responses are combined, and the time histories of both the quasi static and whipping responses are evaluated for a given operating condition (sea state, speed & heading). Finally, for each structural detail, the rainflow counting method is used to evaluate the fatigue damage for both the quasi static and the nonlinear dynamic (quasi-static + whipping) responses. By comparing the two sets of results, the fatigue reduction factor due to whipping is defined as a measure of the whipping influence on fatigue. Due to the simplifications of the slamming model, the whipping simulations are extremely fast so that all the relevant operating conditions can be accounted for within a very reasonable CPU time. The method is implemented into the numerical tool SLAMA [2], by combining the Bureau Veritas hydro structure interaction tool HOMER (structural response), [3], and the OpenFoam CFD tool (slamming force coefficients), [4]. The proposed methodology is demonstrated on the evaluation of the fatigue life of the different structural details of an FPSO.

2 Methods and tools

The basic assumption of the proposed model is that the whipping response can be superimposed over the linear quasi static structural response. In that respect the model can be seen as a weakly coupled. This assumption, together with the simplified slamming model, allows for extremely fast evaluation of the combined quasi-static and dynamic (whipping) structural response, for any given sea state representation. Indeed, the calculation time for a 3-hour duration of the sea state is around 10 to 15 seconds. This allows for consistent consideration of the whole operational profile of the unit within reasonable CPU time. The method combines the Bureau Veritas hydro structure interaction tools HYDROSTAR/HOMER (structural response), [3], [5], [6], and the OpenFoam CFD tool (slamming force coefficients). The overall methodology for evaluation of fatigue life with whipping effects included, consists of the main steps listed in Table 1. Within the present study the Bureau Veritas hydro structure interaction tools are used but any other equivalent tools can also be used, provided that the relevant calculation data are transferred to whipping model (SLAMA) in a correct format.

Table 1. Overview of the methodology steps and associated tools

Analysis type	Scope	Applied tool
Quasi static	Rigid body seakeeping analysis	HYDROSTAR
	Structural analysis on coarse mesh	HOMER/NASTRAN
	Evaluation of the local stress RAO's	HOMER/NASTRAN
	Linear spectral fatigue analysis	STARSPEC
Hydroelastic (Whipping)	Dry modal analysis	NASTRAN
	Wet modal analysis	HOMER & NASTRAN
	Evaluation of slamming coefficients	OpenFioam
	Whipping analysis	SLAMA
	Nonlinear fatigue analysis by rainflow counting	STARSPEC + SNOOPY

HYDROSTAR, [5], is the potential flow 3D diffraction radiation tool based on Boundary Integral Equation Method (BIEM). It allows for full linear and second order hydrodynamic analysis of the stationary floating structures. The HYDROSTAR simulations are performed in frequency domain and the typical outputs for different physical quantities (motions, velocities, relative motions...) are given in terms of the RAO's (Response Amplitude Operators). For a given sea spectrum, the equivalent response signal in time domain, can be obtained by reconstruction of the frequency domain data, after the wave spectra is discretised into a certain number of independent frequencies. The time domain signals of relative motions and relative velocities are used to identify the impact conditions (time instant of impact, relative position and the impact velocity) for a given position on the body.

NASTRAN is the classical commercial 3DFE software for very general linear and nonlinear structural analyses, [7], and here it is used in combination with the Femap pre- and post-processing tool. NASTRAN supports variety of the most common finite elements which were needed to perform the different structural analyses. For the needs of the present study NASTRAN was used within the HOMER framework which allows for the evaluation of the wet structural modes through the coupling with HYDROSTAR.

HOMER is the hydro-structure interaction analysis tool, [3], [6], developed by Bureau Veritas. HOMER combines the NASTRAN structural response analysis tool with the HYDROSTAR hydrodynamic loading analysis tool. HOMER allows for performing both the quasi static and the dynamic hydro-structural analyses.

STARSPEC is the statistical and time domain postprocessing tool allowing to perform the short term and long term analyses of the given response, [8]. It includes both the spectral analysis in frequency domain, and the rainflow counting for the analysis of the time domain signals.

SNOOPY is the library of the Python open-source scripts, for various aspects of wave body interaction analyses, which is provided by Bureau Veritas.

OpenFoam is a CFD open-source tool based on the Finite Volume discretisation. Besides the standard version, simulations performed in this study are conducted in the framework of Foam-extend, using NavalHydro Pack developed at the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture. In-house code is developed particularly for the naval hydrodynamic problems featuring two-phase flow with the sharp interface between the fluid and air [4]. Mathematical model is based on the incompressible two-phase flow where the density and the temperature for both fluids are considered constant.

3 Theoretical aspects of the whipping model

The numerical modeling of the global hydroelastic response of floating units (springing and whipping) is extremely complex since it requires full coupling of the hydrodynamic and structural solutions at each time step of the simulation. The most common hydroelastic models involve a structural model of the ship, a hydrodynamic model of the fluid and a coupling method ensuring that the interaction effects are properly accounted for. The structural model is usually a 3D Finite Element Model (FEM) or a nonuniform beam model (Euler-Bernoulli, Timoshenko, Vlasov), and the fluid-structure coupling effects are commonly calculated by using the potential flow theory, [9]. In addition to the difficulties related to the numerical modelling of the pure seakeeping behavior, the modelling of the slamming represents probably the most critical point, at least within the potential flow theory models. Indeed, the fully consistent numerical model for 3D slamming, within the potential flow theory does not exist today. For that reason, most often the 2D slamming models (most advanced being the Generalized Wagner model) are used in combination with the strip theory approach. However, and in spite of all the recent developments, it is fair to say that none of the proposed methods which are based on potential flow theory, can model fully consistently the whipping phenomena (see [10] for review).

In principle, the hydroelastic model tests or the 3D CFD simulations should be more reliable, but they remain very expensive and cannot be practically applied for industrial projects, where a large number of sea state conditions (several thousands) need to be accounted for. That is why simplified numerical models are needed in practice, and one of those models is proposed here. As already mentioned, the key assumption of the proposed whipping model is that the quasi static and dynamic structural responses can be evaluated separately and summed up together in the postprocessing phase. Based on that assumption, it is possible to use the classical diffraction-radiation numerical codes (HYDROSTAR here) and combine them with the simplified slamming models and the structural vibration models. The diffraction-radiation modelling being the classical one, here we describe more in detail the approach which is used for the evaluation of the dynamic structural response, and the simplified approach used for the evaluation of the slamming loading.

3.1 Evaluation of the vibratory response by wet modal approach

The dynamic model which is used here is based on the use of wet modal decomposition. Furthermore, the typical natural frequencies of the hull girder being relatively high, the added mass matrix associated with those modes (calculated by [5]) is evaluated at infinite frequency. This fact makes the natural modes orthogonal which allows the use of the simple Duhamel integral (for each mode) for the evaluation of the dynamic response. In order to properly introduce the wet modal approach, the basic principles of the modal analysis (dry and wet) are first discussed.

3.1.1 Wet modal approach

The wet modal analysis starts with the evaluation of the dry modes using the commercial software NASTRAN. In mathematical wording this reduces to the resolution of the following eigenvalue system:

$$([\mathbf{K}] - (\lambda_i^p)^2 [\mathbf{M}]) \{\mathbf{U}\} = \{\mathbf{0}\} \quad (1)$$

where $[\mathbf{K}]$ and $[\mathbf{M}]$ are the high dimensional stiffness and mass matrices of the whole 3DFE model, λ_i^D denotes the dry natural frequencies and the vector $\{\mathbf{U}\}$ contains all the degrees of freedom of the 3DFE model. The solution of this eigenvalue problem gives the dry natural frequencies λ_i^D and the corresponding mode shapes $\{\mathbf{h}^D\}_i$:

$$\{\mathbf{h}^D\}_i = \{u_1^D \ \theta_1^D \ u_2^D \ \theta_2^D \ \dots \ u_N^D \ \theta_N^D\}_i^T \quad (2)$$

where u and θ represent nodal translations and rotations, respectively. Once the natural mode shape is defined, the distribution of other relevant physical quantities, for that particular mode, can be deduced e.g. stresses, internal loads:

$$\sigma_i^D(\mathbf{x}), M_{yi}^D(\mathbf{x}), F_{zi}^D(\mathbf{x}) \dots \quad (3)$$

Dry natural modes have a very important property of orthogonality which means that:

$$\{\mathbf{h}^D\}_i^T \{\mathbf{h}^D\}_j = C_i \delta_{ij} \quad \delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} C_i & i = j \\ 0 & i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where the constant C_i depends on the normalization which is adopted when defining the natural modes.

Due to the orthogonality properties of the natural modes, the dynamic modal equation can be rewritten in its (dry) modal form (damping is omitted for the sake of simplicity and will be introduced later):

$$[\mathbf{m}]\{\xi^D\} + [\mathbf{k}]\{\xi^D\} = \{\mathbf{f}^D\} \quad (5)$$

where the modal mass matrix $[\mathbf{m}]$, the modal stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{k}]$ and the modal excitation force vector $\{\mathbf{f}^D\}$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathbf{m}] &= [\mathbf{H}^D]^T [\mathbf{M}] [\mathbf{H}^D], \\ [\mathbf{k}] &= [\mathbf{H}^D]^T [\mathbf{K}] [\mathbf{H}^D], \\ \{\mathbf{f}^D\} &= [\mathbf{H}^D]^T \{\mathbf{F}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

with the mode shapes matrix $[\mathbf{H}^D]$ defined as:

$$[\mathbf{H}^D] = [\{\mathbf{h}^D\}_1 \ \{\mathbf{h}^D\}_2 \ \dots \ \{\mathbf{h}^D\}_{N_n}] \quad , \quad (N \times N_D). \quad (7)$$

What is important to note is that the number of degrees of freedom in equation (5), is equal to the number of modes N_D , and the matrices $[\mathbf{m}]$ and $[\mathbf{k}]$ are diagonal.

3.1.2 Wet modal analysis

The external hydrodynamic force vector $\{\mathbf{f}^D\}$ in the dynamic equation (5) can originate from various sources and can depend on the structural response too. In the present context of floating bodies, the external forces depend on the motions, velocities, and accelerations of the wetted body surface. In addition, there exists a part which is response independent, and which represents pure excitation induced by the incident wave field. These forces are usually represented in terms of the pure excitation $\{\mathbf{f}^E\}$, the added mass matrix $[\mathbf{a}]$, the damping matrix $[\mathbf{b}]$ and the restoring matrix $[\mathbf{c}]$:

$$\{\mathbf{f}^D\} = \{\mathbf{f}^E\} + (\omega^2[\mathbf{a}] - i\omega[\mathbf{b}] - [\mathbf{c}])\{\xi^D\} \quad (8)$$

so that we can rewrite the dynamic motion equation (5), in frequency domain, as:

$$[-\omega^2([\mathbf{m}] + [\mathbf{a}]) + i\omega[\mathbf{b}] + [\mathbf{k}] + [\mathbf{c}]]\{\xi^D\} = \{\mathbf{f}^E\}. \quad (9)$$

It should be noted that the added mass and damping matrices usually depend on the wave frequency ω . However, as already mentioned, here we assume the high frequency range, so that these matrices are taken as their infinite frequency values. From equation (9) we can now deduce the ‘‘wet’’ eigenvalue problem in the form:

$$[[\mathbf{k}] + [\mathbf{c}] - (\lambda_i^W)^2([\mathbf{m}] + [\mathbf{a}])] \{\xi^D\} = \{\mathbf{0}\}. \quad (10)$$

The solution of this eigenvalue problem gives the wet natural frequencies λ_i^W , and the wet natural mode shapes as a function of the dry natural mode shapes. The number of wet modes is not necessarily the same as the number of dry modes even if, most often, it is taken to be the same. Here we denote the number of wet modes by N_W and we define the vector $\{\mathbf{d}\}_i$ as the vector containing the modal participation factors of the dry modes to each wet mode:

$$\{\mathbf{d}\}_i = \{d_1 \ d_2 \ \dots \ d_{N_D}\}_i^T. \quad (11)$$

Because the added mass matrices are taken to be constant, at their infinite frequency limit, it follows that the modal participation vectors $\{\mathbf{d}\}_i$ are also orthogonal.

3.1.3 Evaluation of the dynamic structural response

In order to calculate the instantaneous response of the different physical quantities, the time dependent modal amplitudes need to be evaluated. Since the distribution of the physical quantities is known for each dry mode (3) the dry modal amplitudes $\xi_i^D(t)$ need to be known at the end of simulations. When the dry modal approach is used, they can be obtained directly by solving the dynamic equation in dry modal space:

$$([\mathbf{m}] + [\mathbf{a}])\{\xi^D(t)\} + [\mathbf{b}]\{\dot{\xi}^D(t)\} + ([\mathbf{k}] + [\mathbf{c}])\{\xi^D(t)\} = \{\mathbf{f}^E(t)\}. \quad (12)$$

Once the dry modal amplitudes are known, the instantaneous value of any physical quantity (e.g. the stresses $\Sigma(\mathbf{x}, t)$ at particular point) can be deduced by the following relation:

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_D} \xi_i^D(t) \sigma_i^D(\mathbf{x}). \quad (13)$$

The disadvantage of the dry modal approach is that the system of equations (12), which has the fully populated matrices $[\mathbf{a}]$, $[\mathbf{b}]$ and $[\mathbf{c}]$, needs to be integrated in time by classical numerical integration schemes. In principle, this fact does not represent an enormous problem. However, it is much more convenient to solve the dynamic equation in wet modal space because the dynamic equation can be decoupled and solved for each wet mode separately using the approach which is much more computationally efficient.

We first note that, following the wet modal analysis presented in Section 3.1.2, that the dry and wet modal amplitudes can be related to each other by the following expression:

$$\{\xi^W\} = [\mathbf{D}]^T \{\xi^D\}. \quad (14)$$

This allows to rewrite the dynamic equation (12) in wet modal space as follows:

$$([\mathbf{m}] + [\mathbf{a}])[\mathbf{D}]\{\xi^W\} + [\mathbf{b}][\mathbf{D}]\{\xi^W\} + ([\mathbf{k}] + [\mathbf{c}])[\mathbf{D}]\{\xi^W\} = \{\mathbf{f}^{EW}\} \quad (15)$$

where the matrix $[\mathbf{D}]$ is given by:

$$[\mathbf{D}] = [\{\mathbf{d}\}_1 \{\mathbf{d}\}_2 \dots \{\mathbf{d}\}_{N_W}] \quad , \quad (N_D \times N_W) \quad (16)$$

With this in mind we can rewrite the dynamic equation (12) in wet modal space:

$$(-\omega^2[\mathbf{m}^W] + i\omega[\mathbf{b}^W] + [\mathbf{k}^W])\{\xi^W\} = \{\mathbf{f}^{EW}\}, \quad (17)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathbf{m}^W] &= [\mathbf{D}]^T([\mathbf{m}] + [\mathbf{a}])[\mathbf{D}], & [\mathbf{b}^W] &= [\mathbf{D}]^T[\mathbf{b}][\mathbf{D}], \\ [\mathbf{k}^W] &= [\mathbf{D}]^T([\mathbf{k}] + [\mathbf{c}])[\mathbf{D}], & \{\mathbf{f}^{EW}\} &= [\mathbf{D}]^T\{\mathbf{f}^E\}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Because the modal participation vectors $\{\mathbf{d}\}_i$ are orthogonal, it follows that the mass matrix $[\mathbf{m}^W]$ and the stiffness matrix $[\mathbf{k}^W]$ are diagonal too, which means that we can write:

$$m_i^W \xi_i^W(t) + b_i^W \dot{\xi}_i^W(t) + k_i^W \xi_i^W(t) = f_i^{EW}(t), \quad i = 1, N_W \quad (19)$$

The solution of the dynamic equation for each mode is obtained using the Duhamel integral as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_i^W(t) &= \frac{1}{m_i^W \lambda_{id}^W} \int_0^t f_i^{EW}(\tau) e^{-\zeta_i^W \lambda_{id}^W (t-\tau)} \sin[\lambda_{id}^W (t-\tau)] d\tau, \\ \lambda_{id}^W &= \lambda_i^W \sqrt{1 - (\zeta_i^W)^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where λ_i^W are the wet natural frequencies and ζ_i^W is the modal damping expressed as a percentage of the critical damping b_{ic}^W :

$$b_{ic}^W = 2 \sqrt{k_i^W m_i^W}. \quad (21)$$

Once the wet modal amplitudes are known the dry modal amplitudes can be calculated from (14) and the time history of any physical quantity can be evaluated using the expression of type (3).

3.1.4 Choice of the relevant natural modes

Theoretically, the total number of natural modes (dry or wet) is equal to the number of degrees of freedom of the system. However, there is only a limited number of natural modes (here denoted by N_D) which is of interest for a particular study. The interest for certain modes is driven by the properties of the external loading, i.e. by the possibility that the particular modes will be excited by a given excitation. The natural modes are usually classified with respect to the natural frequencies starting from the lowest ones. Most often, for ship-like bodies, the lowest natural frequencies are associated with the global (hull girder) structural deformations modes in vertical plane e.g. the vertical bending modes (1 node, 2 nodes ...). However, for some specific floating units, the torsional modes or horizontal bending modes might become the lowest ones, as for example in the case of the container ships where the torsional modes are those having the lowest natural frequency. Also, in some cases, another (relatively) local vibration modes might become relevant and coupled with the global hull girder modes. That is precisely the case here where the natural frequencies of the local vibration modes of the flare tower become close to the hull girder natural frequencies which result in the coupled natural frequencies and modes which combine the global and local deformations of the structure. In any case, in the present context, where the slamming is the main excitation source, only the few first natural modes, whatever they are, are of concern because other modes have higher natural frequencies, and their dynamic amplification will not be significant.

3.2 Evaluation of the vibratory response by wet modal approach

The procedure for the evaluation of the slamming loading consists of two main steps:

1. Identification of the slamming events,
2. Evaluation of the slamming loading.

3.2.1 Identification of the slamming events

The occurrences and the impact conditions are determined from the precalculated seakeeping simulations. For that purpose, the time history of the body motions and the relevant free surface elevation are reconstructed in time

domain from their precalculated RAO's. From these time histories, it is possible to monitor the emergence and the impact of the representative parts of the body which are likely to experience slamming. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Basic principles for the identification of slamming events.

Once the occurrence of impact is determined the relative position of the hull and the corresponding relative velocity of the representative points can be determined. Those data are used as input to the slamming model which is discussed below.

3.2.2 Evaluation of the slamming loading

The slamming loads are evaluated by the simplified formula which was calibrated using the CFD simulations. The simplified slamming model is inspired from the work presented in [1], [11], and [12]. In that respect the slamming force is assumed to act in the vertical direction only and is given in the following form:

$$F_z(t) = \rho C_s(\phi) [V_{rz}(t)]^3 t, \quad (22)$$

where:

- ρ Density of water (1025 kg/m³),
- $V_{rz}(t)$ Vertical relative velocity at the moment of impact,
- $C_s(\phi)$ Slamming force coefficient,
- ϕ Roll angle.

The slamming force coefficient depends mainly on the local geometry before and during the impact and, that is why it is assumed to depend on the roll angle ϕ only. This slamming force coefficient and the duration of impact are calibrated through a limited number of CFD simulations at the fore and the aft parts of the body. For that purpose, only a limited part of the body was modelled because the numerical tests showed that the influence of the rest of the hull on the local loads is negligible. The forces are obtained by integrating the pressure over the part of the body surface as shown in Figure 2. In the present case, during the calibration process, it was observed that the slamming force is linearly dependent on roll angle so that the slamming coefficient can be written in the following form:

$$C_s(\phi) = C_s(0) + K_s \cdot \phi \quad (23)$$

where ϕ is the roll angle.

Figure 2. Evaluation of the slamming loads by CFD simulations. Left – OpenFOAM simulations, Right – Integration surface.

It should be noted that the dynamic slamming force component only is included in the slamming model and the hydrostatic pressure part is excluded. It is clear that the proposed slamming model can be criticized from many points of view, however it is believed that it gives a fair estimation of the order of magnitude of the slamming impulsive loading. That is why it is advised to check the sensitivity of the final whipping response to small variations of the slamming coefficient $C_s(\phi)$.

3.3 Evaluation of the whipping response

Once the time history of the slamming force is evaluated, it is projected on the wet natural modes using the following expression:

$$\{\mathbf{f}^{EW}\} = [\mathbf{D}]^T \{\mathbf{f}^E\} = [\mathbf{D}]^T \{\mathbf{F}_s\}^T \{\mathbf{h}^D\}, \quad (24)$$

where $\{\mathbf{F}_s\}$ is slamming force reduced to a reference point simplified slamming model (22).

The Duhamel integral (20) gives the time histories of the wet modal amplitudes $\xi_i^W(t)$ and the whipping induced structural stresses can be evaluated using the expression (13) together with (14).

In order to illustrate the overall procedure, an example of 3 hours simulations for a particular sea state is presented in Figure 3 for a total simulation time of three hours, and in Figure 4 for the time signal around the typical whipping event.

Figure 3. Quasi-static (top), whipping (middle) and total (bottom) stresses for a typical case. 3 hours duration of the sea state.

Figure 4. Quasi-static (top), whipping (middle) and total (bottom) stresses for a typical case. Detailed results around a typical whipping event.

3.4 Evaluation of the fatigue life

The fatigue calculation is performed through a Miner's Rules. The relevant S-N curve (in this study taken from this study are taken from [13]) is defined by the parameters m and K , so that the maximum number of cycles until failure for a given stress range $\Delta\sigma$ is given by:

$$N(\Delta\sigma) = \frac{K}{(\Delta\sigma)^m} \quad (25)$$

The fatigue damage for a given sea state D_{ss} is given by:

$$D_{st} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_c} \frac{n_j}{N_j} \quad (26)$$

where:

n_c Total number of stress ranges,

n_j Number of cycles at stress range $\Delta\sigma_j$,

N_j Number of cycles to failure at stress range $\Delta\sigma_j$.

The total long term fatigue damage D_{lt} is given by:

$$D_{lt} = \frac{T_{ref} * 3600 * 24 * 365.24}{T_{st}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{ss}} D_{st}^i * prob(i) \quad (27)$$

where:

T_{ref} Reference lifetime (30 years),
 T_{st} Short term duration of the i -th sea state (3 hours),
 N_{ss} Total number of sea states,
 D_{st}^i Short term damage for i -th seas state,
 $prob(i)$ Probability of occurrence of the i -th sea state.

The number of cycles can be obtained either using the spectral analysis or using the rainflow counting method. Once the long term fatigue damage is evaluated the fatigue life is given by:

$$Fatigue\ life = \frac{T_{ref}}{D_{lt}} \quad (28)$$

The expression (26) is valid for arbitrary type of the stress time history i.e. both for the quasi-static and hydroelastic (with whipping effects included) structural responses. For the present application the whipping coefficient, for a given sea state, is defined as the ration between the fatigue damage with whipping effects included D_{st}^{Wh} and the quasi static fatigue damage D_{st}^{QS} :

$$C_{Wh} = \frac{D_{st}^{Wh}}{D_{st}^{QS}} \quad (29)$$

so that the fatigue life for the case with whipping effects included is given by:

$$D_{lt}^{Wh} = \frac{T_{ref} * 3600 * 24 * 365.24}{T_{st}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{ss}} C_{Wh}^i * D_{st}^{QS_i} * prob(i). \quad (30)$$

The whipping coefficient C_{Wh}^i is determined after calculating the number of cycles, using the rainflow counting method, for the quasi static case and the whipping case separately but for exactly the same definition of the sea state (same wave components).

4 Numerical setup and results

The developed mathematical model is illustrated considering the fatigue life of selected structural details of an FPSO, Figure 5, with following principal dimensions:

Length between perpendiculars	$L_{PP} = 345.30$ m
Breadth (moulded)	$B = 60.0$ m
Depth (at side)	$H = 33.80$ m
Depth (at centreline)	$H = 34.30$ m
Design draught (moulded)	$T_d = 23.78$ m
Maximum storage capacity	$Capacity = 261,532.7$ m ³ .

Figure 5. Global FE model of the considered FPSO.

Two representative points need to be selected to which slamming loads are being reduced: one at the fore part and one at the aft part of the FPSO as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Representative points for slamming analysis.

The vertical position of these points can be varied and used as a parameter for calibration of the model. As already indicated in Section 3.2.1 the impact is defined to occur at the instant when the representative point, which previously emerged from the water, hits the water surface with threshold velocity.

The analysis has been performed for four different loading conditions characterized by relevant draught and service percentage, as follows:

- LC09 $T=23.81$ m 15%
- LC15 $T=19.51$ m 35%
- LC18 $T=17.06$ m 35%
- LC24 $T=12.85$ m 15%

The relative position of the characteristic points at the fore and aft part of the FPSO, with respect to the different draught is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Relative positions of characteristic points at different draughts (Loading conditions).

Details of the wave conditions are given in [14] and in Table 2 we present only the directional distribution, with directional percentage of total significant wave height in Figure 8.

Table 2. Distribution of total significant wave heights and primary spectral peak directions

Hs(m)	DIRECTION(°)																Freq	%	Mean Dir	
	N	NNE	NE	ENE	E	ESE	SE	SSE	S	SSW	SW	WSW	W	WNNW	NW	NNW				
0.0	0.5	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0.01	145.6	
0.5	1.0	19	51	266	342	146	135	93	104	138	143	49	6	5	4	3	8	1512	2	99.2
1.0	1.5	55	370	1622	2303	2314	1826	1303	784	577	505	105	26	8	11	9	24	11842	15.64	97
1.5	2.0	100	882	4137	4266	3161	3089	2799	2516	2291	1330	169	49	24	3	4	16	24836	32.8	103.3
2.0	2.5	68	840	3481	2557	1530	1404	1654	1965	2753	2367	348	85	27	15	8	19	19121	25.25	117.1
2.5	3.0	37	482	1722	1169	709	552	556	944	1519	1928	360	136	35	10	8	8	10175	13.44	131.9
3.0	3.5	22	170	721	428	288	212	211	365	651	1039	361	93	27	10	4	6	4608	6.09	149.2
3.5	4.0	3	41	222	134	101	108	90	115	229	555	199	53	10	4	3	0	1867	2.47	168.1
4.0	4.5	0	15	69	34	22	33	33	63	74	265	146	40	15	1	0	0	810	1.07	189.2
4.5	5.0	0	2	24	12	17	10	18	30	36	127	97	30	7	0	0	0	410	0.54	196.6
5.0	5.5	0	1	5	8	5	0	8	12	17	68	74	29	2	0	0	0	229	0.3	208.4
5.5	6.0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	6	12	28	58	17	0	0	0	0	124	0.16	215
6.0	6.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	20	43	0	0	0	0	0	66	0.09	223.2
6.5	7.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	4	32	0	0	0	0	0	39	0.05	222.2
7.0	7.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	7	19	0	0	0	0	0	29	0.04	219
7.5	8.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	10	0	0	0	0	0	11	0.01	226.9
8.0	8.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	8	0	0	0	0	0	9	0.01	226.6
8.5	9.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	10	0.01	231.4
9.0	9.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	4	0.01	227.2
9.5	10.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	207.8
10.0	10.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	NaN
10.5	11.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	NaN
Freq		304	2854	12269	11257	8294	7370	6765	6906	8309	8391	2091	564	160	58	39	81	75712		
%		0.4	3.77	16.2	14.87	10.95	9.73	8.94	9.12	10.97	11.08	2.76	0.74	0.21	0.08	0.05	0.11			
Mean Hs		1.98	2.12	2.1	1.94	1.86	1.87	1.95	2.12	2.28	2.58	3.28	3.13	2.8	2.33	2.19	1.85			

Figure 8. Directional percentage of total significant wave height.

Four structural details at different locations have been considered, i.e. topside support, flare tower connection and two flare tower joints. The top-down procedure has been applied to determine local stresses needed for fatigue computation [15], and therefore fine mesh local models of the relevant details have been generated, Figures 9 to 12, with their position along the ship hull shown in Figure 13.

Figure 9. Fine mesh model of the topside support.

Figure 10. Fine mesh model of flare tower connection.

Figure 11. Fine mesh model of flare tower joint 1 (left) and its zoomed view (right).

Figure 12. Fine mesh model of flare tower joint 2 (left) and its zoomed view (right).

Figure 13. Positions of local models along the ship hull.

Hydrodynamic meshes used in computations are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Hydrodynamic meshes.

Initial computations involve hydrostatic balancing and evaluation of still water internal loads and stresses. Just for the illustration, here the still-water stresses within the global model and Flare tower joint 2 for LC09 are shown, Figures 15 and 16., while the results of the natural vibration analysis have been summarized in Tables 3 and 4. After stress RAOs are determined, Figure 17, the linear spectral fatigue has been computed for all details and loading conditions by means of Starspec [8], and further on the modal stresses for the elements with lowest fatigue lives have been determined in order to calculate the fatigue with whipping effect.

The fatigue results are summarized in Table 5. With respect to the operational profile of the unit, the combined fatigue life (FL) is evaluated using the following relation:

$$FL(\text{Combined}) = 0.15 \cdot FL(\text{LC09}) + 0.35 \cdot FL(\text{LC15}) + 0.35 \cdot FL(\text{LC18}) + 0.15 \cdot FL(\text{LC24}). \quad (31)$$

At the same time, the Whipping Fatigue Reduction Factor (WFRF) is defined as follows:

$$WFRF = \frac{FL(QS + Whip)}{FL(QS)} \quad (32)$$

where:
 $FL(QS)$ Quasi static fatigue life (linear)
 $FL(QS + Whip)$ Fatigue life with whipping included (nonlinear).
 The values in Table 5 represent the mean values obtained after running the SLAMA software for 7 different sea states representations (seed numbers) and taking the mean of 7 runs.

Figure 15. Still-water stresses (MPa) within the FPSO structure, LC09, deformed view.

Figure 16. Still-water stresses (MPa) in flare tower joint 2, LC09.

Table 3. First 3 structural natural frequencies of FPSO for different loading conditions

Mode no.	Frequency (Hz)							
	LC09		LC15		LC18		LC24	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
7	0.474	0.413	0.475	0.434	0.476	0.445	0.477	0.471
8	0.564	0.480	0.603	0.482	0.608	0.486	0.616	0.567
9	0.606	0.588	0.611	0.591	0.633	0.592	0.687	0.627

Table 4. Dry natural mode shapes of FPSO for different loading conditions

Mode no.	LC09		LC15		LC18		LC24	
	XZ Plane	YZ Plane						
7								
8								
9								

Figure 17. Example of stress RAOs (MPa/m), flare tower joint 2, LC09.

Table 5. Summary of the fatigue life (years) and the whipping fatigue reduction factors (WFRF)

Fine mesh model	LC09		LC15		LC18		LC24		Combined		WFRF
	QS	QS+Whip	QS	QS+Whip	QS	QS+Whip	QS	QS+Whip	QS	QS+Whip	
Topside	63.38	68.35	76.51	76.49	80.75	80.66	68.63	68.63	75.59	75.55	0.99
FLTC	1020.3	1019.1	1319.07	324.02	1194.02	308.70	695.96	694.13	1137.02	478.44	0.42
FLTJ1	338.4	338.2	462.58	299.64	416.62	134.25	329.73	328.98	407.94	251.94	0.62
FLTJ 2	1397	1382.78	1349.86	1188.65	1257.92	774.67	970.71	954.79	1267.9	1037.80	0.82

5 Conclusion

An efficient numerical model for evaluation of the whipping response is proposed. The basic assumption of the overall methodology is that the quasi-static structural response and the dynamic whipping response can be evaluated independently and combined together in the postprocessing phase. This is justified by the fact that the hull girder natural frequencies are much higher than the wave frequencies. The critical point in the analysis is the

accuracy of the slamming force model which was significantly simplified and evaluated using the precalculated slamming coefficients. These slamming coefficients were determined using the 3D CFD simulations (OpenFoam software) for different impact speeds. Thanks to extremely low computational cost, proposed model allows for consistent evaluation of the whipping induced fatigue for whole operational profile of the vessel. It also allows for the evaluation of the variability of the whipping correction factor, with respect to the sea state representation (seed number). This is an important aspect of the problem because the whipping response is highly nonlinear phenomena.

The methodology was applied for the evaluation of the fatigue life of the structural details of an FPSO for which important interaction of the first hull girder natural mode and the natural mode of the flare tower could happen due to the similar natural frequencies. This might produce an important whipping contribution to the fatigue life of the structural details at the connection point between the flare tower and the hull. It has been shown, in this study, that the reduction of fatigue life can be very significant indeed, and the fatigue life can be reduced more than twice for some of those details. However, due to the fact that the original quasi-static fatigue life is extremely large (several hundreds or even thousands of years) the structural details still remain very safe from fatigue point of view. It has also been shown that, for the structural details of the topside connections in midship region, whipping response has almost no influence and the whipping correction factor remained close to one. In spite of that the fatigue life of the topside connection remains much shorter than that for the flare tower details, because for topside details the quasi static fatigue life is much shorter.

References

- [1] Sun Z., Sui X.P., Korobkin A., Zou L. & Zong Z. Slamming force decomposition with gravity effect, *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, Vol. 114, 2022.
- [2] Vladimir N. & Senjanovic I. *SLAMA – Theory and User's manual*, University of Zagreb, 2023.
- [3] De Lauzon, L., Benhamou, A. *Homer 2.2.0 – User manual*, Bureau Veritas, 2020.
- [4] Vukcevic V., Jasak H. & Malenica S., 2016.: “Decomposition Model for Naval Hydrodynamic Applications, Part II: Verification and Validation”, *Ocean Engineering*, Vol. 121, pp. 76-88.
- [5] Bureau Veritas. *HYDROSTAR For Experts – User manual*, 2016.
- [6] Malenica S., Derbanne Q., Sireta F.X., Bigot F., Tiphine E., De-Hauteclocque G. and Chen X.B. “HOMER - Integrated hydro-structure interactions tool for naval and off-shore applications”, *Int. Conference on Computer Applications in Shipbuilding*, Busan, Korea, 2013.
- [7] MSC Software. *MD Nastran User's guide*. Newport Beach, California, USA, 2010.
- [8] Bureau Veritas. *Starspec – User guide*, 2016.
- [9] Malenica, Š., Senjanović, I., Vladimir, N. Hydro structural issues in the design of ultra large container ships, *Brodogradnja*, Vol. 64, No. 3, 2013., pp. 323-347.
- [10] ISSC: Committee II.2 Dynamic Response, *Proceedings of the 20th International Ship and Offshore Structures Congress*, 2018.
- [11] Jensen J.J., Pedersen P.T., Shi B., Wang S., Petricic M., Mansour A.E. Wave induced extreme hull girder loads on container ships, SNAME paper SMTC-072-2008, 2008.
- [12] Zhao, R., Faltinsen, O. Water Entry of Two-dimensional Bodies, *J. Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 246, 1993., pp. 593-612.
- [13] American Bureau of Shipping. *Guide for Fatigue Assessment of Offshore Structures*, USA, 2020.
- [14] Petrobras: Metocean data, Project: NORTHERN SANTOS BASIN PRE-SALT SYSTEMS, Technical specification No. I-ET-3A36.00-1000-941-PPC-001 – Rev. D.
- [15] Sireta, F.X., Derbanne, Q., Bigot, F., Malenica, Š., Baudin, E. Hydroelastic response of a ship structural detail to seakeeping loads using a top-down scheme, *31st International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering - OMAE*, ASME, Brasil, 2012.